

Implementation of Custom Processing Using libwebrtc

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Abstract: This technical note describes the implementation of custom video and audio processing using **libwebrtc**^a, with a focus on the virtual MCU system **bres**^b. The approach enables remote video compositing and transmission in the context of WebRTC-based media workflows. We discuss both the custom receiving and sending pipelines, and demonstrate a framework for extending libwebrtc functionality for specialized applications such as remote production.

Fig. 1: bres overview

^a <https://webrtc.googlesource.com/src/webrtc>

^b <https://github.com/mixi-video-dev/bres>

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1. Introduction

The **libwebrtc** library is available in several programming languages, including C++, Go, and Python. Among these, the C++ implementation is directly utilized by web browsers such as Chrome and Firefox, providing stable interoperability with browser-based clients. Due to its highly object-oriented, abstracted, and interface-driven design, libwebrtc allows seamless access from browser scripts and facilitates extensibility.

In this note, we present a case study of **custom sending and receiving processes** in libwebrtc, using bres as an illustrative example.

2. Design and Method

The **bres** system functions as a virtual MCU (Multipoint Control Unit).

- Multi-channel video (VP8) and audio (Opus) streams are ingested from an SFU.
- Chroma key compositing is performed based on user-defined attributes, such as:
 - scaling factors
 - positional parameters (x, y)
 - chroma key threshold values
- The composited streams are transmitted back to the SFU as separate **send-only** channels.
- The implementation is currently verified on **macOS 10.15 and later**, and operates through direct SFU connectivity.

3. Custom Receive Processing

In scenarios where WebSocket-based signaling is employed, the operational chain for libwebrtc objects related to media reception

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proceeds as follows:

Fig. 2: Receive Operations-Chain

- **VideoSinkInterface<VideoFrame>** and **AudioTrackSinkInterface** instances implement event callbacks for received data.
- Custom user logic may be defined in:
 - **VideoSinkInterface<VideoFrame>::OnFrame** for video frame handling
 - **AudioTrackSinkInterface::OnData** for audio data handling

Listing 1: video-reciever.cc

```
class VideoSinkInterfaceImpl:
public rtc::VideoSinkInterface<webrtc::VideoFrame>
public:

// rtc::VideoSinkInterface<webrtc::VideoFrame> interfaces.
virtual void OnFrame(
    const webrtc::VideoFrame& frame
) override
{
    rtc::scoped_refptr<webrtc::VideoFrameBuffer> buffer(
        frame.video_frame_buffer());
    rtc::scoped_refptr<webrtc::I420BufferInterface>
        i420_buffer = buffer->ToI420();
    char* rgb = NULL;
    if (!bres::pop_frame(inst_, EVENT_TYPE_EMPTY_IMAGE, &
        rgb)) {
        LOG("not enough empty-image buffer(pop_frame)[%s]\n",
            inst_->channel_id.c_str());
        return;
    }
    // ffmpeg -f rawvideo -video_size 640x360 -pix_fmt
    rgb32 1l_img.bin
    if (i420_buffer->width() != WND_WIDTH || i420_buffer->
        height() != WND_HEIGHT) {
        rtc::scoped_refptr<webrtc::I420Buffer>
        scaled_buffer = webrtc::I420Buffer::Create(WND_WIDTH,
            WND_HEIGHT);
        scaled_buffer->ScaleFrom(*i420_buffer);
        //
        libyuv::I420ToABGR(
            scaled_buffer->DataY(),
            scaled_buffer->StrideY(),
            scaled_buffer->DataU(),
            scaled_buffer->StrideU(),
            scaled_buffer->DataV(),
            scaled_buffer->StrideV(),
            (unsigned char*)rgb,
            WND_WIDTH * 4,
            scaled_buffer->width(),
            scaled_buffer->height());
    } else {
        libyuv::I420ToABGR(
```

```
i420_buffer->DataY(),
i420_buffer->StrideY(),
i420_buffer->DataU(),
i420_buffer->StrideU(),
i420_buffer->DataV(),
i420_buffer->StrideV(),
(unsigned char*)rgb,
i420_buffer->width() * 4,
i420_buffer->width(),
i420_buffer->height());
}
//
bres::push_frame(inst_, EVENT_TYPE_CURRENT_IMAGE, rgb)
;
}
```

Listing 2: fifo.cc

```
case LWS_CALLBACK_CLIENT_RECEIVE:
{
    memcpy(&inst->recv_buffer[0], in, len);
    inst->recv_written = len;
    std::string res((char*)inst->recv_buffer, inst->
        recv_written);
    auto json = nlohmann::json::parse(res);
    const std::string type = json["type"];
    //
    if (type == "offer") {
        bres::push_event(
            inst,
            EVENT_ORDER_WEBSOCKETS_TO_WEBRTC,
            EVENT_TYPE_OFFER,
            res
        );
    }
}
```

To enhance modularity and clarity, event flows should be **separated by FIFO-based event queues**, which isolate contexts such as:

- WebSocket signaling events (e.g., OFFER, CANDIDATE, PING)
- **webrtc::PeerConnection** events (e.g., OnFrame, OnData, OnSuccess)

Fig. 3: Separated with FIFO

4. Custom Send Processing

The sending chain leverages libwebrtc 's source interfaces:

- For video, frames are injected via AdaptedVideoTrackSource::OnFrame(...) at a frame rate of **30 FPS**.

- For audio, samples are injected via `AudioTransport::RecordedDataIsAvailable(...)` at **48 kHz, 16-bit, 2-channel resolution**.

This design allows the system to transmit user-defined processed streams in real time.

Fig. 4: Send Operations-Chain

Listing 3: video-render.cc

```
namespace movie {
class VideoRender:
public rtc::AdaptedVideoTrackSource
{
public:
VideoRender(): AdaptedVideoTrackSource(4) {}
virtual ~VideoRender() {}
// rtc::AdaptedVideoTrackSource interface
virtual bool is_screencast() const override {
return(false); }
virtual absl::optional<bool> needs_denoising()
const override { return(false); }
virtual webrtc::MediaSourceInterface::SourceState
state() const override { return(SourceState::kLive); }
virtual bool remote() const override { return(
false); }
//
virtual void AddRef() const override {}
virtual rtc::RefCountReleaseStatus Release() const
override {
return(rtc::RefCountReleaseStatus::
kOtherRefsRemained);
}
public:
void Render(char* img, unsigned length, unsigned
width, unsigned height) {
int64_t timems = rtc::TimeMillis();
rtc::scoped_refptr<webrtc::I420Buffer> buffer
= webrtc::I420Buffer::Create(width, height);
rtc::scoped_refptr<webrtc::I420Buffer> scaled
= webrtc::I420Buffer::Create(640, 360);
buffer->InitializeData();
//
libyuv::ConvertToI420(
(uint8_t*)img,
length,
buffer->MutableDataY(),
buffer->StrideY(),
buffer->MutableDataU(),
buffer->StrideU(),
buffer->MutableDataV(),
buffer->StrideV(),
0, 0,
width, height,
buffer->width(),
buffer->height(),
libyuv::kRotate0,
libyuv::FOURCC_ARGB);
//
scaled->ScaleFrom(*buffer);
```

```
// webrtc::I420Buffer::SetBlack(buffer.get());
webrtc::VideoFrame frame = webrtc::VideoFrame
::Builder()
.set_video_frame_buffer(scaled)
.set_timestamp_rtp(
0)
.set_timestamp_ms(
rtc::TimeMillis())
.set_timestamp_us(
rtc::TimeMicros())
.set_rotation(
webrtc::kVideoRotation_0)
.build();
OnFrame(frame);
};
};
```

5. Image Compositing

Ingress video frames are **synchronized and composited** before transmission to a dedicated channel. This compositing pipeline enables integration of multiple visual sources and controlled placement, making it suitable for virtual production scenarios.

Fig. 5: Video compositing

6. Conclusion

This note has outlined the design and implementation of **customized sending and receiving pipelines** using libwebrtc. The proposed framework demonstrates how user-defined logic can be incorporated into the standard WebRTC stack.

References

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